

Validation of android-based mobile application for retrieving network signal level

Kehinde A. Adeniji¹, Nazmat T. Surajudeen-Bakinde², Olusegun O. Omitola³, Adedayo Ajibade⁴

^{1,3,4}Department of Electrical/Electronics and Computer Engineering, Afe Babalola University, Ado Ekiti, Nigeria

²Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, University of Ilorin, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the evolvement of mobile devices which perform sophisticated functions have been on the rise. Mobile applications which solved engineering challenges are now available due to the high computational capabilities, large random access memory and storage location of the mobile devices. An Android application called signal detect, which measures network signal strength value from 2G-4G received on an android mobile device has been developed using android app development environment called Android studio. Validation becomes necessary because different readings were obtained on smartphones with different specifications. Two validation techniques were used to validate the data obtained. To know the efficiency of the application; a field strength meter was used to compare the readings received on the mobile device with the meter. It was observed that there is a time lag on the received values of the mobile device to the field strength meter. Therefore, a moving average technique was used to correlate the two data which increased the correlation coefficient to about 0.85.

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Corresponding Author:

Adeniji Kehinde Adetunji

Department of Electrical & Electronics and Computer Engineering

Afe Babalola University, Ado Ekiti, Nigeria

Email: kehintheadeniji@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, communication system applications are utilized in the day-to-day activities of human lives, these include telecommunication, terrestrial television, transportation (maritime & air), military and security. Communication system engineering applications have evolved from the era of line telegraphy, radio telephony to real-time communication through the use of sophisticated smartphones that can perform various tasks including online shopping, cloud gaming, financial processes, controller, measurements and mapping etc [1-4]. Contemporary smartphones are versatile portable computers-on-chip that exploit the flexibility conferred on them by the existence of operating systems in this case Android that manages and controls operations of the smartphones depending on the architecture. Simple push email and web services were the definition of smartphones application some years back but now have geared up with applications which need data networks to perform its functions [5]. Therefore, smartphones are usually managed by the combination of different network frameworks of computing, sensors and communication systems [6, 7].

In Africa, especially in Nigeria, the services provided by the network infrastructure of service providers do not meet the specified standards set by both local and global regulators [8]. As most network signals received by smartphones often fall short of what can be classified as good quality of service (QoS) in terms of signal strength, resource distribution, connection and traffic control, security, call drop rates, data

transfer speed, and so on [9-11]. Various factors such as noise, computation speed of mobile switching centre, propagation mechanism, handover, path-loss, network infrastructure setup and atmospheric conditions can affect the quality of signal strength as it travels between the transmitter and the receiver [12-15]. Therefore, it is wise to explore ways and means of utilizing especially whereas in this case the versatile smartphone is used as a vehicle for building indigenous android applications that can support germane uses of smartphones for development of suitable apps for communication engineering to solve challenges, enhance teaching, and research.

An application is simply a set of instructions written in a specific language which are used to perform user-defined tasks [16]. These user-defined tasks are developed using various high-level languages available such as JAVA, C++, C#, Python, and so on. Mobile applications are hosted on mobile devices and performed user-defined tasks by interacting with the various hardware components on mobile devices [17], [18]. There are about 2.7 million apps available for download on Google play store [19]. A look at the play store shows Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp are the most downloaded with each having more than 1 billion downloads.

There are many android applications on google play store available on-purchase or free which can retrieve and display signal strength value in dBm of the mobile network signal received on an android phone. Network cell info lite, location finder & GSM mapper and RF signal tracker are few relevant android apps that can measure GSM, 3G and LTE signal received on a smartphone. Network cell info lite as presented in [20] displays received signal strength value and a display gauge which responds to the changes in the value received on the mobile device. The major challenge of the app is that it is not user-friendly. Location finder & GSM mapper given in [21] shows the received signal strength with the base transceiver station (BTS) information serving the smartphone. These applications do not display the pictorial plot of the signal strength values plot in real-time against the time been investigated. The RF signal tracker is an android app which also shows the received signal strength value and the signal-noise-ratio (SNR) level of the smartphone. Similarly, this app does not display the pictorial plot of the signal strength values [22].

Therefore, an Android-based mobile application for retrieving received network signal level has been developed in this work. The proposed app called SignalDetect can detect received signal strength values for 2G, 3G and 4G networks, network bar gauge, pictorial plot and most importantly the introduction of timestamp of the received signal strength values on the application this is because time is a critical factor in predicting the behavior of network, propagation modeling and effective network coverage of BTS. The uniqueness of this work is that the work has been able to validate signal strength with respect to android app using field strength meter. The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the design block, programming languages and important libraries of the developed app, while Section 3 discusses the results obtained from the developed app tested on various smartphones and the performance evaluation of the developed app at different specifications is presented. Further analysis with a field strength meter was used to validate the results obtained from the developed app with two validation techniques; and finally, Section 4 concludes the paper.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The design and implementation of Android apps are achieved on the integrated development environment (IDE) called Android Studio, which is based on either JAVA or C/C++ programming languages [23]. To develop an android application, an IDE like Android Studio or Eclipse, software development kit (SDK), the java software development kit (JDK) and a virtual device called an emulator are all requisites. A developed Android application can be packaged and made available for download on different platforms such as google play store, and Amazon Appstore. Each application developed in Android Studio contains one or more modules with source code files and resource files such as Android app modules, library modules and google app engine modules. The most important of the app build files are found in the following folders:

- a) Manifests: Contains the AndroidManifest.xml file, which describes the fundamental characteristics of the app.
- b) Java: Contains the MainActivity.java code files, having an activity class that script the user defined tasks of the app.
- c) Res: Contains all non-code resources, such as XML layouts, UI strings, and bitmap images, which generally describe the app user interface.

It is imperative to mention the important libraries in developing the application as these libraries created the means of interacting with the hardware features of the smartphone as in this case of the register, baseband processor, and system clock. `Androidtelephony.signal strength` [24] is the function when invoked contains mobile phone signal strength related information as received on the mobile device and will detect the related information as network signal switches automatically between 2G, 3G and 4G. The signal strength

value received is an arbitrary strength unit (ASU), which is just a representation of the rate at which the phone is able to update its signal power and quality by connecting to a nearby BTS. ASU basically measures the same thing as dBm, but on a more linear scale. As dBm is the acceptable form of measuring signal strength, (1) converts ASU to dBm:

$$\text{dBm} = (2 * \text{ASU}) - 113 \quad (1)$$

(2) and (3) snippets transformed the ASU value received on an android mobile phone to dBm.

$$\text{mSignalStrength} = \text{SignalStrength.getGsmSignalStrength}() \quad (2)$$

$$\text{mSignalStrength}_{\text{dBm}} = (2 * \text{mSignalStrength}) - 113 \quad (3)$$

The other important library is `android.telephony.telephonymanager`, which designed a graphical tool known as network bar that displays the signal strength in bar as received on a mobile phone [25]. The phone manufacturer and operating system driving the mobile phone determines the design of the network bar showed on the phone. `Android.os.systemclock` [26] simply synchronized the system time on the mobile phone with the timestamp widget on the application and `jjoeb64`. `Graphview` does a real-time plot of the data against the time. Figure 1 shows the design flow of developing Android application.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the application flow

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of the developed SignalDetect app was tested on three smartphones. These smartphones and their features are listed in Table 1. Figures 2, 3 and 4 show the SignalDetect running on Nokia 6, Samsung A-6 and Samsung S7 Edge respectively. As shown in Table 1, the major smartphone manufacturers do not use the same components in the design of their phones which resulted in different interfaces obtained from the developed application on smartphones. The major reason is that Android UI (user interface) interactive and view components such as text-view, edit-view and buttons which design the user interface are all embedded in the android operating system. Since the versions of operating systems installed on the smartphones differ from one another, the interfaces are also different.

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Table 1. Smartphones and specifications

S/N	Smartphone	Specification
1	Nokia 6	Technology: GSM, HSPA, LTE Operating System: Android 7.1.1 (Nougat) Chipset: Qualcomm MSM8937 Snapdragon 430 (28 nm) CPU: Octa-core 1.4 GHz Cortex-A53 GPU: Adreno 505 RAM: 3GB
2	Samsung A-6	Technology: GSM, HSPA, LTE Operating System: Android 8.0 (Oreo) Chipset: Exynos 7870 Octa (14 nm) CPU: Octa-core 1.6 GHz Cortex-A53 GPU: Mali-T830 MP1 RAM: 3 GB
3	Samsung S7 Edge	Technology: GSM,HSPA,LTE Operating System: Android 6.0 (Marshmallow) Chipset: Qualcomm MSM8996 Snapdragon 820 (14 nm) CPU: Quad-core(2x 2.15 GHz Kyro & 2 x1.6 GHz Kyro) GPU: Adreno 530 RAM: 4 GB

Figure 2. Signaldetect on nokia 6 smartphone

Figure 3. signaldetect on samsung A-6

Figure 4. Samsung S7 edge smartphone respectively

3.1. Performance evaluation

Apart from the aforementioned features of SignalDetect, it was used to collect data simultaneously along with other existing apps on the same smartphones with similar specifications. The data collected was simulated as shown in Figure 5, with a correlation coefficient of 0.99 among them when computed. This

implies that the developed app retrieved accurate data appropriately on the smartphone. The developed app was used to obtain samples on the smartphones shown in Table 1, all smartphones were initiated at the same time and each collected received signal strength level samples. Figure 6 shows the performances of the app on the various smartphones. The plot of signal strength values obtained from SignalDetect on the three different smartphones indicates that the data obtained on the smartphones differs from one another as a result of the composition of the smartphones. Consequently, the signal strength value received is a function of the processes (hardware and software of a smartphone) that delivered this value. Since the compositions of the phones are different, the performance of the app on the smartphones was slightly different as expected.

Hence, this justifies the different values in terms of signal strengths obtained in Figure 6. Since the diversity of hardware structure of smart phones vary from each other, hence the performance of the receiver sensitivities on the smart phones due to thermal noise and degradation are not similar which makes the values obtained on them to vary as well. Equally, smartphones manufacturers have different shifting approaches used on the smart phones to covert the ASU values of the received signals to values in dBm, this leads to differences in values obtained on the smartphone at the same location.

Figure 5. Measured signal strength plot of the three apps

Figure 6. Performance of signaldetect on the three smartphones

3.2. Validation

As the values obtained on the smartphones running SignalDetect are slightly different, it will be wise to validate it with a standard measuring device before using to ascertain the correlation coefficient and necessary adjustment to be considered. A field strength meter and nokia smartphone running SignalDetect

shown in Figure 7 were used to obtain the signal strength values. Figure 8 shows the plot of field strength meter and smartphone readings values obtained from them respectively; the plot shows that there is a time delay on the smartphone before the values are registered on the application. A moving average technique was done to shift the data by one to improve the plot, as shown in Figure 9. This improves the correlation coefficient between the two data to about 0.85. Thus a solid positive relationship exists between the two data obtained as both measured variables responded to the fluctuation of signal strength received from the BTS.

Figure 7. Field strength meter and smartphone reading displays

Figure 8. Signal strength plot for field strength meter and nokia

Figure 9. Moving average plot between field strength meter and nokia

3.2.1. Scatter plot and regression line

The two data sets are plotted on a scatter plot, the pattern of the resulting points on the scatter plot helps to determine if there is a presence of a strong correlation between the two variables. The plot shows good visualization of the correlation between the data sets. The value of one variable determines the position

on the horizontal axis and the value of the other variable determines the position on the vertical axis of the scatter plot. The values obtained from the field strength meter and the developed app were plotted using scatter plot function with (4):

$$Plot = scatter(X, Y) \tag{4}$$

where x and y are the field strength and developed app dataset respectively.

Figure 10 shows the scatter plot of the data sets for the field strength meter and the developed app. A strong correlation between the data sets is indicated by the regression line which passes through the data plotted because the data points are uniformly distributed above and below the regression line. This implies strongly correlated data between the two variables.

Figure 10. Scatter plot of signal strength values: field strength meter and nokia

3.2.2. Histogram and shewness

Histogram is a good tool to show the distribution of the obtained data with a normal density curve. Figure 11 shows the comparison of the obtained data with a normal distribution curve. The distributions of the sampled data appear to be left skewed and also the majority of the histograms are considerably peaked relatively to a normal distribution curve.

Figure 11. Histogram of the received signal strength samples

4. CONCLUSION

As smartphone architecture keeps evolving with the introduction of improved hardware, the development of smartphones applications have been enhanced by this improvement. Steps must be taken to mitigate the errors that could arise in the data obtained from such applications as shown that the data collected is a function of the composition of the smart phones. With a correlation coefficient of about 0.85, it is acceptable to use SignalDetect as the relationship between the two data is significant enough to be considered for usage. However, appropriate steps need to be taken to cover up for the error that will arise due to the hardware features of the smartphone. Therefore, this research shows that validation of android mobile apps is necessary especially before its usage for research and performance evaluation. SignalDetect can be installed on any android device with a minimum API level 16 to the latest release ones and can be used by any network planner, network providers and regulators, and on any research work that involves measuring the mobile signal strength of a coverage area.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Kehinde A. Adeniji was born in Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. He received the BEng (Hons) degree in computer system engineering from the University of South Wales, United Kingdom in 2014 and completed his master's degree thesis in electrical and electronics engineering at University of Ilorin, Nigeria. He worked briefly with MTN Telecom Nigeria as a quality control rep in 2012. Since 2014, he has been a lecturer with the department of electrical, electronics and computer engineering, Afe Babalola University, Ado-ekiti, Nigeria. His research interests include web and mobile computing, 4IR, wireless communication, software development, system simulations and signal processing. Mr. Adeniji was a recipient of the lion laboratory award from University of South Wales in 2014 for best graduating student, and also a registered member of The Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN).

Nazmat T. Surajudeen-Bakinde was born in Kwara State, Nigeria. She received the BEng. and MEng. degrees in electrical and electronics engineering from the University of Ilorin, Nigeria and the Ph.D. degree in electrical and electronics engineering from University of Liverpool, United Kingdom. She is an Associate Professor with the University of Ilorin, Nigeria. She is the author of more than 50 articles. Her research interests include telecommunication, radio propagation, optimization techniques and Internet of Things. Dr Surajudeen-Bakinde is a member (M) of IEEE; she is a Resource Person for the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), Abuja. She is an advocate and champion of girl child education under the Development Research Projects Centre (DRPC). She was formerly the acting head of department, electrical and electronics engineering, University of Ilorin

Olusegun O. Omitola was born in Ibadan, Nigeria. He received B.Tech degree in Computer Engineering from Ladoko Akintola University of Technology (LAUTECH), Nigeria, in 2007 and M.Sc. in Mobile Computing and Communications from the University of Greenwich, London, United Kingdom in 2012. He recently completed his Ph.D. degree in Electronics Engineering from the University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. He is currently a lecturer at the department of Electrical, Electronic and Computer Engineering, Afe Babalola University, Nigeria. He has published several papers in international refereed journals. His interests include mobile and wireless communications, femtocells, LTE/LTE-A, and mobile ad-hoc networks. Omitola is a registered engineer with Council for Registration of Engineering in Nigeria (COREN), and a professional member of British Computer Society (BCS).

Adedayo Ajibade was born in Ibadan, Nigeria. He received BSc. degree in Electronic and Electrical Engineering from Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria in 2006. He obtained a Master of Science degree in Communication Systems Engineering from the University of Portsmouth, England in 2009. He is currently pursuing his PhD degree in Power Line Communication Systems from Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria, where he is also a research member of the Centre for Research in Electrical Communication (CRECO), Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. His research interests are in the areas of wireless communication, power line communication, MIMO-OFDM antenna systems